

1 **Running heading: Fate of ewe lamb**

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7 **Genetic and non-genetic factors associated with the fate of maiden ewe lambs:**
8 **slaughtered without ever lambing versus retained for breeding¹**

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ABSTRACT

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The decision on which ewe lamb to retain versus which to sell is likely to vary by producer based on personal preference. What is not known, however, is if any commonality exists among producers in the characteristics of ewe lambs that influence their eventual fate. The objective of the present study was to determine what genetic and non-genetic factors associate with the fate of maiden ewe lambs. The fate of each ewe lamb born in the present study was defined as either subsequently: 1) having lambled in the flock, or 2) was slaughtered without any recorded lambing event. A total of 9,705 ewe-lamb records from 41 crossbred flocks were used. The logit of the odds of the ewe lamb being retained for lambing was modeled using logistic regression. Variance components were then estimated for the binary trait representing the fate of the ewe lamb using animal linear and threshold mixed models. The genetic correlations between fate of the ewe lamb and pre-weaning, weaning or post-weaning live-weight were also estimated. From the edited dataset, 45% of ewe lambs born entered the mature flock as ewes. Ewe lambs reared as singles, with greater levels of heterosis but lower levels of recombination loss, born to dams that lambled for the first time as hoggets, with greater breed proportion of the Belclare, Suffolk, Texel and Llyen breeds were more likely ($P < 0.001$) to eventually lamb in the flock than be slaughtered without ever lambing. Irrespective of the age of the animal when weighed, heavier ewe lambs were more likely to eventually lamb ($P < 0.001$). The genetic SD and direct heritability of fate of the ewe lamb estimated in the univariate linear model was 26.58 percentage units and 0.31 (SE= 0.03), respectively; the heritability was 0.30 when estimated using the threshold model. The corresponding direct heritability of fate of the ewe lamb estimated in the bivariate analyses with live-weight ranged from 0.29 (SE= 0.03; pre-weaning weight) to 0.35 (SE= 0.04; post-weaning weight). The genetic correlations estimated between fate of the ewe lamb and the live-weight traits were weak to moderate but strengthened as the age of the ewe lamb at weighing increased. Results

51 from this study provide an understanding of the factors producers consider when selecting
52 females for retention versus slaughter which may form useful parameters in the development
53 of a decision support tool to identify suitable ewe lambs for retention.

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55 **Keywords:** efficiency, genetics, sheep, survival, weight

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INTRODUCTION

58 With a replacement rate of approximately 20 to 30% in many sheep populations
59 (Wolfova et al., 2009; Bohan et al., 2019), a large number of surplus ewe lambs are produced
60 annually. In Ireland, 70% of sheep farmers retain home-bred females as replacements (Bohan
61 et al., 2017) which suggest that many females are sold off-farm either to other flocks or directly
62 to an abattoir. The decision on which ewe lamb to retain versus which to sell is likely to vary
63 by producer based on personal preference. What has not been established heretofore is if any
64 commonality exists among producers in the characteristics of ewe lambs that influence their
65 eventual fate.

66 There is a plethora of studies that have documented factors, like live-weight, to be
67 associated with fertility traits, such as age at first calving or lambing, in both nulliparous cattle
68 (Buskirk et al., 1995; Wathes et al., 2008; Brickell et al., 2009) and sheep (Jorgenson et al.,
69 1993). Similarly, in an analysis of Irish dairy herds, Kelleher et al. (2016) reported that only
70 76% of what they deemed to be eligible dairy heifers actually calved. Such studies have,
71 however, failed to investigate the reasons why such nulliparous animals did not subsequently
72 enter the mature herd/flock. Hence, the objective of the present study was to investigate the
73 genetic and non-genetic factors associated with the fate of maiden ewe lambs in an Irish sheep
74 population. Results will be useful in firstly understanding the factors producers consider when
75 selecting females for retention versus slaughter, but also as input parameters for a decision

76 support tool in identifying suitable ewe lambs for retention; the latter could earmark females
77 of preferred characteristics and sire line as potential candidates from which to select from, but
78 could also complement other information available when selling lambs.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

81 **Data**

82 Data on a range of animal-specific events including date of birth, date of lambing, live-
83 weight records and slaughter information were extracted from the Irish national sheep database
84 hosted by Sheep Ireland (<http://www.sheep.ie>). Since the data originated from a pre-existing
85 database, it was not necessary to obtain animal care and use committee approval to conduct the
86 study. Data were available on 43,419 nulliparous ewe lambs born in 112 flocks where slaughter
87 and lambing data were recorded between the yr 2010 and 2018, inclusive.

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89 *Fate of the nulliparous female*

90 The fate of each ewe lamb born was defined as either having subsequently: 1) lambed
91 at least once in the flock, or 2) was slaughtered without ever having lambed. As the fate of ewe
92 lambs born in 2018 was yet to be determined, only ewe lambs born between 2010 and 2017
93 were retained for analysis; 3,676 records were omitted. Ewe lambs that lambed at least once
94 prior to 28 mo of age (irrespective of their fate thereafter) were coded as having lambed
95 (McHugh et al., 2017). Ewe lambs that were slaughtered ≤ 365 d of age, and without a recorded
96 lambing date, were coded as having been slaughtered. Ewe lambs with a slaughter or death
97 date > 365 d of age, or no recorded slaughter, death or lambing date prior to 28 mo of age, were
98 removed; a total of 19,009 records were removed. Only flocks where $\geq 25\%$ of ewe lambs were
99 slaughtered within a given yr were retained; 5,255 records from 144 flock-yr were removed.

100 Finally only ewe lambs that were retained in their birth flock until slaughter or first lambing
101 were considered. Following edits, records from 15,394 nulliparae ewe lambs remained.

102 *Rearing status*

103 Data were also available on the birth and rearing type of each ewe lamb. Birth type of
104 the ewe lamb was defined as the recorded number of full-sib lambs (including the ewe lamb
105 herself) born in the same litter as the ewe lamb (alive or dead); only birth types between one
106 (singles) and four (quadruplets) were retained for analysis. Litter rearing size was defined as
107 the number of lambs (including the ewe lamb herself) that was reared in the litter of the ewe
108 lamb at d 7 post-lambing; only litter rearing sizes between one and three were retained.

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110 *Live-weight*

111 Ewe lamb live-weight recorded at birth, pre-weaning, weaning and post-weaning were
112 also available and were defined based on the editing criteria used in the national genetic
113 evaluations (McHugh et al., 2017); 92% of ewe lambs had at least two live-weight records. For
114 birth weight, only lambs weighed within the first 48 hours after birth and weighing between 2
115 and 9 kg were retained. Pre-weaning live-weight was defined as the live-weight taken between
116 20 and 65 d of age; only records of lambs weighing between 12 and 32 kg were retained.
117 Weaning weight was defined as the live-weight recorded between 66 and 120 d of age; only
118 live-weight records between 20 and 55 kg were retained. Post-weaning weight was defined as
119 live-weight measured between 121 and 180 d of age; only live-weight records between 25 and
120 65 kg were considered. Muscle and fat depth were also measured when weighing the animal
121 post-weaning; only muscle depth measurements between 20 to 35 mm and fat depth measures
122 between 1 to 15 mm were retained. Average daily gain (ADG) between consecutive live-weight
123 records was calculated for each lamb; only calculated ADG values between 100 and 650 g/d
124 were retained which resulted in 1,054 ADG records being discarded.

125 Data were also available on dam parity, breed composition and both heterosis and
126 recombination loss coefficients of each ewe lamb and dam. Dam parity was categorized as 1,
127 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 or ≥ 7 . Age of the dam at first lambing was categorized as lambing either: 1) between
128 8 and 18 mo of age, or 2) between ≥ 18 and 28 mo of age. The breed proportion of each ewe
129 lamb and dam for the five major performance recording breeds in Ireland namely, Belclare,
130 Charollais, Suffolk, Texel and Vendeen were calculated. Heterosis and recombination loss
131 coefficients were calculated for each ewe lamb as $1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \text{sire}_i \cdot \text{dam}_i$ and $1 - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\text{sire}_i^2 + \text{dam}_i^2}{2}$,
132 respectively where sire_i and dam_i are the proportion of breed i in the sire and dam, respectively.
133 Heterosis and recombination loss coefficients were subsequently grouped into distinct classes
134 based on the frequency distribution of the respective coefficients. For heterosis four distinct
135 classes were formed: less than 10%, 10% to 50%, 51% to 99%, and 100%. For recombination
136 loss, two classes were formed: less than 10% and 10% to 50%.

137 Each ewe lamb was allocated to a contemporary group based on flock by month-year
138 of birth. Only contemporary groups with some variation in the fate of the ewe lamb were
139 retained for the analysis; 938 records from 12 flock-years were removed. Contemporary groups
140 with less than 5 records were not considered further. Following all edits, 9,705 ewe lamb
141 records from 41 flocks remained.

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146 **Statistical analyses**

147 *Phenotypic analysis*

148 The logit of the odds of the ewe lamb being retained on-farm as a ewe (i.e., subsequently
149 lambled herself) was modeled using logistic regression in PROC GENMOD (SAS Inst. Inc.,
150 Cary, NC) while accounting for the binomial distribution of the errors. A multiple regression
151 model was built up using stepwise forward-backward regression, including interactions of
152 biological interest; the significance threshold for entry and exit of variables into/from the model
153 was set at 5%. Factors considered for inclusion as fixed effects in the model were: birth type
154 of the ewe lamb, rearing type of the ewe lamb, contemporary group, parity of dam, age at first
155 lambing of dam, the breed proportion of each ewe lamb and dam for six breeds (Belclare,
156 Charollais, Lleyn, Suffolk, Texel and Vendeen) each fitted as separate covariates, and the
157 heterosis and recombination loss classes of both the ewe lamb and her dam. Lamb live-weight
158 at birth, pre-weaning, weaning and post-weaning, ultrasound fat and muscle depth, as well as,
159 ADG between the four weight time points were also considered individually in different
160 iterations of the model.

161

162 *Genetic analysis*

163 For the genetic analysis, only 7,571 ewe lambs who had both a sire and dam recorded
164 were retained. Variance components were estimated for the fate of the ewe lamb using
165 univariate linear mixed animal models fitted in ASReml (Gilmour et al., 2009). For comparison
166 purposes, a univariate threshold model for fate of the ewe lamb was also fitted. For the fate of
167 the ewe lamb, the fixed effects employed in all models were based on the results from the
168 phenotypic analysis, except that lamb live-weight, ADG or breed proportion of the ewe lamb
169 or dam were not considered in the models. For both the linear univariate and threshold model,
170 an additive direct animal effect was included as a random effect. Variance components
171 estimated using a sire threshold model was almost identical to those estimated using the animal
172 threshold model and are therefore not discussed. Including a maternal genetic or permanent

173 environmental effect did not improve the fit of the models. The pedigree of each animal was
174 traced back to the founder population; breed groups were fitted via the pedigree.

175 A series of bivariate models were also investigated whereby ewe lambs with no known
176 fate (i.e. had no recorded slaughter date or lambing date) that originated from the same flock-
177 yr as the ewe lambs with a known fate and had a recorded live-weight at either pre-weaning,
178 weaning or post-weaning were reintroduced into the dataset; 8,266 ewe lambs with live-weight
179 records were added to give a total of 15,837 records. When the dependent variable was pre-
180 weaning, weaning or post-weaning live-weight, the fixed effects included in the model were:
181 age at weighing, contemporary group of flock-date of weighing, birth type of the ewe lamb,
182 rearing type of the ewe lamb, dam parity, age of dam at first lambing, and ewe lamb and dam
183 heterosis and recombination class. A direct additive genetic effect and maternal dam effect
184 were both included as random effects for all live-weight traits.

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RESULTS

187 *Phenotypic analysis*

188 On average, 45% of the ewe lambs had a recorded lambing date, whereas the remaining
189 55% were slaughtered ≤ 365 d of age. The mean age at first lambing of ewe lambs was 611
190 (SD= 163) d; the median age at first lambing was 726 d. For the ewe lambs that were
191 slaughtered, the mean (and median) age at slaughter was 226 (SD= 54) d.

192 Factors associated with the fate of the ewe lamb were rearing type, age of dam at first
193 lambing, lamb heterosis and recombination class, dam heterosis class, the ewe lamb breed
194 proportion for Belclare, Texel and the Llyen breed as well as the dam breed proportion of the
195 Belclare and Suffolk breed ($P < 0.001$); the fate of the ewe lamb did not differ by birth type, ewe
196 parity or class of recombination loss in the ewe. Ewe lambs reared as singles were 1.37 times
197 ($P < 0.001$) and 1.96 times ($P < 0.001$) more likely to eventually lamb compared to ewe lambs

198 reared as twins and triplets, respectively. Ewe lambs born to dams that lambed for the first time
199 as hoggets were 1.90 times (95% CI: 1.31 to 2.74; $P < 0.001$) more likely to, they themselves,
200 subsequently lamb compared to ewe lambs born to dams that lambed for the first time as ewe
201 lambs.

202 Ewe lambs with greater levels of heterosis were more likely to eventually lamb (Table
203 1); relative to ewe lambs with $< 10\%$ heterosis, ewe lambs with 51% to 99%, and 100% were
204 1.75 times ($P < 0.001$) and 1.31 times ($P < 0.05$) more likely to eventually lamb, respectively
205 (Table 1). Ewe lambs with lower levels of recombination loss (i.e., $< 10\%$) were 1.52 times
206 (95% CI: 1.19 to 1.95; $P < 0.001$) more likely to eventually lamb relative to ewe lambs with 10
207 to 50% recombination loss. Ewe lambs born to dams with lower levels of heterosis were also
208 more likely to eventually lamb (Table 1).

209 The fate of the ewe lamb differed by the breed proportion of the Belclare, Suffolk, Texel
210 and Llyen in the ewe lamb herself. A ewe lamb of 50% Belclare breed proportion had a 13.0
211 percentage unit greater predicted probability of eventually lambing relative to a ewe lamb with
212 a Belclare breed percentage of 25%. Ewe lambs born to dams with Belclare and Suffolk
213 bloodlines had a lower probability of subsequently lambing; dams with a 50% breed percent
214 of Belclare or Suffolk had a respective 4.19 percentage unit and 6.92 percentage unit lower
215 predicted probability of producing ewe lambs who themselves eventually lambed compared to
216 dams with 25% breed percent of the respective breeds.

217 Irrespective of the time period of weighing, heavier ewe lambs were more likely to
218 eventually lamb. A ewe lamb with a 1 SD heavier live-weight relative to the mean birth, pre-
219 weaning, weaning and post-weaning weight had a 13.4, 30.7, 36.8 and 31.8 percentage unit
220 greater predicted probability of eventually lambing compared to a ewe lamb that was 1 SD
221 lighter than the mean live-weight at each respective time points (Fig. 1). When live-weight was
222 included as the dependent variable and after adjusting for all of age at weighing, breed

223 proportion and birth and rearing type, ewe lambs that lambed were, on average, 0.27 kg (6%
224 of the overall population mean), 1.68 kg (9% of the overall population mean), 3.21 kg (10% of
225 the overall population mean) and 3.32 kg (9% of the overall population mean) heavier
226 ($P<0.001$) at birth, pre-weaning, weaning and post-weaning, respectively compared to ewe
227 lambs that were slaughtered at ≤ 365 d of age. Similarly ewe lambs that grew faster up to
228 weaning were more likely ($P<0.001$) to eventually lamb; the fate of the ewe lambs did not
229 differ by ADG post-weaning. Ewe lambs with greater fat and muscle depth recorded post-
230 weaning were more likely to eventually lamb; a ewe lamb with a fat depth of 7 mm (i.e., 1 SD
231 higher than the mean fat depth) had a 7.9 percentage unit greater predicted probability of
232 eventually lambing compared to a fat depth of 3 mm (1 SD lower than the mean fat depth). A
233 ewe lamb with a muscle depth 1 SD deeper than the mean muscle depth (31 mm) had an 11.0
234 percentage unit greater predicted probability of eventually lambing compared to a ewe lamb
235 with a fat depth 1 SD less than the mean muscle depth (25 mm; $P<0.001$). The phenotypic
236 factors associated with live-weight traits are presented elsewhere (McHugh et al., 2017;
237 Fitzmaurice et al., 2019) and are therefore not discussed.

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239 *Genetic analysis*

240 The genetic SD and heritability of fate of the ewe lamb estimated from the linear
241 univariate model was 26.58 percentage units and 0.31 (SE= 0.03), respectively (Table 2). The
242 corresponding heritability of fate of the ewe lamb estimated using the threshold model was
243 almost identical at 0.30 (SE= 0.01); therefore only results from the linear model analysis of
244 fate of the ewe lamb are presented hereon in. The direct heritability for the live-weight traits
245 ranged from 0.10 (SE= 0.02) for pre-weaning live-weight to 0.27 (SE= 0.04) for post-weaning
246 live-weight. The maternal heritability for the live-weight traits reduced with lamb age from
247 0.24 (SE= 0.01) for birth weight to 0.07 (SE=0.02) for post-weaning weight. The genetic

248 correlations estimated between fate of the ewe lamb and the live-weight traits were weak to
249 moderate but strengthened as the age of the ewe lamb at weighing increased (Table 2). The
250 corresponding phenotypic correlations between fate of the ewe lamb and the live-weight ranged
251 from 0.16 (SE= 0.01) to 0.38 (SE= 0.01). The genetic SD for fate of the ewe lamb estimated in
252 the bivariate analyses with live-weight measures ranged from 24.70 percentage units (weaning
253 weight) to 26.50 percentage units (birth weight); the corresponding heritability of fate of the
254 ewe lamb estimated in the bivariate analyses ranged from 0.29 (SE= 0.03; pre-weaning weight)
255 to 0.35 (SE= 0.04; post-weaning weight; Table 2).

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DISCUSSION

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Intensive sheep production systems globally are typically characterized by large flock sizes with multiple different sub-flocks all being managed differently. This is particularly true pre-lambing where the number of in-utero fetuses detected in mid-gestation is often used to partition the ewes into management groups based on expected litter size, with each group then fed accordingly. The same is true post-lambing, where the management of ewes rearing multiple lambs often differs to those rearing singletons. Furthermore, if males remain entire, then the males may be managed separately to the female flock(s). Hence, the infrastructure and precedence exists to manage different subsets of the flock differently. While some producers may identify candidate replacement females at birth, others may not select females until later in life. In larger flock, such an exercise can become unwieldy. One strategy to facilitate the segregation of candidate ewe lambs for replacement (either for the flock itself or to market as replacements) would be to have a real-time decision support complemented with individual animal identification and genomic information; the latter could be used to estimate breed composition and parentage, enabling breeding values of the animal to be generated for the range of characteristics available. The extent of genotyping of candidate female replacements

273 is intensifying in sheep as a means of more accurately identifying genetically elite females
274 (Rupp et al., 2016). The net return from investing in genotyping females is a function of,
275 amongst others, the proportion of genotyped females that are retained as replacements (Newton
276 and Berry, 2019). This is because if fewer candidate females are selected, then the cost of
277 genotyping the entire cohort of candidate females is diluted across the fewer number of selected
278 females. If the candidate replacement females therefore could be pre-screened based on factors
279 identified in the present study, then fewer candidate females would need to be genotyped,
280 implying a lower overall genotyping cost and thus reduced cost per retained female.

281 The fact that 45% of the females in the present study eventually re-entered the mature
282 flock as replacements implies that there is indeed a huge opportunity to guide the decision on
283 which females to retain. On the flipside, knowledge of the females which are certainly not
284 suitable replacement candidates (i.e., low probability of suitability) can be extremely useful
285 when partitioning out these females for either direct sale or for a management system suited
286 for rapidly growing these females specifically for slaughter. The females could be further
287 segregated on live-weight to produce a more homogenous group but also to advise on the
288 appropriate feeding regime to achieve the desired drafting schedule.

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290 **Risk factors**

291 The literature is generally void of factors associated with the fate of a young female
292 sheep. The results from the present study indicate a greater likelihood of a female lamb
293 becoming a replacement if she was born as a single, to a dam that lambed for the first time as
294 a hogget (i.e., 2-yr old), had greater heterosis levels and had greater ADG recorded pre-
295 weaning. This is not overly surprising since these factors had been shown to associate with
296 lamb live-weight (McHugh et al., 2017) and, with the exception of lamb breed composition,
297 the factors associated with the likelihood of a female lamb becoming a replacement are based

298 on the ewe lamb attaining a heavier live-weight at the point of selection. What may be
299 surprising was the degree of the effect of some of the risk factors on ewe lamb fate and, in
300 some cases, there was double the likelihood of being retained as a replacement when comparing
301 some levels of the risk factors; examples include rearing type with almost twice the likelihood
302 of a singleton being retained than a triplet or almost twice the likelihood of a ewe lamb being
303 retained if born to a hogget compared to being born from a ewe lamb. A singleton ewe lamb,
304 for example, born to a dam that lambed for the first time as a hogget, with 100% heterosis had
305 a 31 percentage unit greater predicted probability of she herself eventually lambing in the flock
306 compared to a ewe lamb born as a triplet to a dam that lambed for the first time as a ewe lamb
307 with <10% heterosis. When lamb live-weight was added as a covariate to the model, the effect
308 of some of the risk factors on ewe lamb fate was actually reversed; in fact, once adjusted to a
309 common live-weight, ewe lambs reared as triplets and twins were 1.21 and 1.60 times (P
310 <0.001) more likely to eventually lamb relative to single reared ewe lambs. This suggests that
311 producers should segregate potential replacements females reared in multiple litters at a young
312 age and ensure that sufficient feed resources are available to these ewe lambs to reach a desired
313 live-weight prior to actual selection.

314 What the analysis undertaken in the present study, however fails to disentangle is the
315 reasons why some females never subsequently lambed while others did. The outcome could be
316 a conscious decision of the farmer not to even consider mating some females, but instead
317 managing them for meat production, but could also be an inability of the female to conceive
318 and establish pregnancy. In some instances of course, the slaughtered females may actually be
319 pregnant. There is a paucity of information on conception rate in nulliparous sheep. However,
320 in their analysis of 19 UK dairy herds, Wathes et al. (2008) stated that only 2.3% of heifers
321 failed to conceive.

322 Notwithstanding these deficiencies, the large estimated genetic standard deviation for
323 ewe lamb fate signifies an underlying genetic variability which could be considered in breeding
324 programs. The existence of a moderate heritability (irrespective of statistical model) implies
325 firstly that there is commonality among producers on the characteristics dictating the fate of
326 the ewe lamb, and secondly that a large quantity of individual progeny data is not actually
327 required to generate accurate estimates of genetic merit for individual sires. The similar
328 heritability estimates for ewe lamb fate estimated using either a linear or threshold model is not
329 unexpected given that the incidence of females in the present study that eventually re-entered
330 the mature flock as replacements was near 50% (i.e., 45%). Moreover, the moderate heritability
331 of ewe lamb fate is similar to that for live-weight (Table 2; Safari et al., 2005) and higher than
332 that generally reported for most fertility traits in sheep (Safari et al., 2005). This therefore
333 implies that it is traits associated with animal size that influences farmer decisions on the fate
334 of the ewe lamb as opposed to an inability to establish pregnancy; this conclusion is consistent
335 with the observed genetic and phenotypic associations detected in the present study between
336 animal live-weight and ewe lamb fate.

337

338 **Deployment of decision support tool**

339 A decision-support tool developed using the parameters derived in the present study to
340 identify candidate replacement females could be invoked at the time of each weighing with the
341 candidate females diverted to a separate management group. At the subsequent weighing,
342 selection could again occur within the candidate replacement group with some females possibly
343 being ejected from the group; likewise, based on the performance data available at the time,
344 females in the other mobs may graduate into the candidate replacement group. The model
345 parameters estimated in the present study could form the basis of the suitability of each lamb
346 as a flock replacement female. The predicted probability of the female being a suitable

347 replacement could be calculated immediately with the available data used to populate the
348 prediction equations generating the results. Ideally, the individual flock data would be used to
349 generate the model parameters, although a large flock would be required to generate precise
350 model solutions. A further option may be to use a Bayesian-type approach where the model
351 solutions from larger datasets (e.g., the present dataset) could act as prior knowledge which
352 could then be combined with model solutions from the flock itself to generate a posterior
353 probability for each lamb of becoming a replacement female.

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355 **CONCLUSIONS**

356 Despite an undoubted contribution of personal preferences to whether or not a ewe lamb
357 is retained within the flock, results from the present study clearly indicate relatively strong
358 consistency among Irish producers at least. The evidence of this was based on the often large
359 odds ratios for some risk factors but also the moderate heritability for ewe lamb fate. Potential
360 therefore exists for the development of a breeding and management decision support tool to
361 inform and make both easier and automated the selection of females for retention as parents of
362 the next generation in the flock.

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416 **Table 1.** Ewe lamb and dam heterosis and ewe lamb recombination odds ratios (upper and
417 lower confidence intervals in parenthesis for fate of ewe lamb
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Trait	Level ¹	Odds Ratio
Ewe-lamb heterosis	<10%	1.00 ^a
	10 to 50%	1.28 (0.93, 1.77) ^a
	51 to 99%	1.75 (1.26, 2.42) ^b
	100%	1.31 (0.99, 1.74) ^a

Dam heterosis	<10%	1.00 ^a
	10 to 50%	0.69 (0.49, 0.99) ^b
	51 to 99%	0.73 (0.51, 1.04) ^{ab}
	100%	0.68 (0.53, 0.85) ^b
Ewe-lamb recombination	<10%	1.00 ^a
	10 to 50%	0.66 (0.51, 0.85) ^b

419 ¹Heterosis class of <10% was the reference category for ewe lamb and dam heterosis, and ewe
420 lamb recombination.

421 ^{a-b}Least square means with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$) from each other.

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430 **Table 2.** Direct genetic SD (σ_g) in percentage units, the direct heritability for the fate of the
431 ewe lamb estimated in the linear model bivariate analyses with the live-weight traits as well as
432 the corresponding genetic (r_g ; standard error in parentheses) and phenotypic (r_p ; standard error
433 in parentheses) correlation.

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Trait	σ_g	h^2_d	r_g	r_p
Birth weight	0.265	0.31 (0.03)	0.22 (0.09)	0.16 (0.01)
Pre-wean	0.251	0.29 (0.03)	0.27 (0.09)	0.27 (0.01)
Wean	0.247	0.29 (0.03)	0.34 (0.08)	0.37 (0.01)
Post-wean	0.256	0.35 (0.04)	0.41 (0.09)	0.38 (0.01)

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436

a.

b.

437

438

c.

d.

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441 **Figure 1.** Predicted probability (continuous line) of eventually lambing for a ewe lamb differing in live-weight as well as the mean live-weight
 442 (dotted line) at a) birth, b) pre-weaning, c) weaning and d) post-wean¹.

443 ¹Where the reference animal was a 50% Suffolk cross lamb reared as a twin, born to a 50% Belclare cross dam that lambed for the first time as a hogget, with heterosis of 10
 444 to 50%, and recombination of 10 to 50%.